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“SILK ROAD ON THE AGENDA AGAIN“

Dr. Murat KARTAL

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SILK ROAD ON THE AGENDA AGAIN

Abstract

Although it is necessary to think more research on the issue that the Silk Road is neither a real road nor a single road, it is the main issue to concentrate on how to supply more benefits in terms of its history and future. Because the Silk Road should be examined under two separate headings in terms of both its usefulness and the benefit to be given to it. To study the "Silk Road" as a term is to refer to a network of roads used by traders for more than 1,500 years since China's Han dynasty began trading in 130 BC. Until 1453 AD, when the Ottoman Empire closed the trade with the West, the importance of this road should be evaluated separately. It is no accident that the German geographer and traveler Ferdinand von Richthofen first coined the term "silk route" in 1877 AD to describe the well-traveled goods route between Europe and East Asia. The term also serves as a metaphor for the exchange of goods and ideas between diverse cultures. The Silk Road was in bad shape with no government to keep it, stretching about 6,437 kilometers through of the world's most challenging landscapes, including the Gobi Desert and the Pamir Mountains. Over time, large inns called caravanserais hosted traveling merchants. Traders carried silk from China to Europe, and other favorite items from Asia included jade and other gemstones, porcelain, tea, and spices. Marco Polo, one of the most famous travelers of the Silk Road, also reflected this road in history with memories (1254 CE -1324 CE). It is difficult to overstate the importance of the Silk Road in history. For religion and ideas spread as fluently as goods along the Silk Road. Today, parts of the Silk Road are on UNESCO's World Heritage List. Our study has created to analyze and characterize the current situation of the Silk Road, which includes Azerbaijan, focusing more on its geography.

Keywords: *Silk Road, Geography of Silk Road, New Silk Road, Old and New History of Silk Road*

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The Silk Road is important as it is a wide trade network connecting Eurasia and North Africa by land and sea. The fact that it got its name from Chinese silk, a valuable commodity that merchants carried throughout these trade networks, is closely related to advances in technology and increasing political stability. The result of this, of course, draws attention as an increase in trade. In AD 14, the Roman historian Tacitus reported that the Imperial Senate had made it illegal for men to wear silk and decided that "Oriental silks should no longer degrade the male sex."¹ However, this ban on silk did not last. Demand for silk continued to drive trade between the Roman Empire, China, India and many places in between. One reason for expanding trade seems to be related to the growth of imperial power. Bringing the East and the West together, the Silk Road has left traces in the political, economic and cultural developments of the countries it passes through. Travelers, traders and missionaries exchanged cultural, scientific, educational and spiritual values. Azerbaijan was on these roads and made significant contributions to the development of this global transit network. It was known from time

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immemorial that the goods and products of Azerbaijani towns and settlements spread along the Silk Road and their towns functioned as centers of culture, science and education. Bilateral land and sea routes connected Azerbaijan with China, Syria, India, Asia Minor, Iran, Egypt, Russia, Arabian Peninsula, North Africa and Europe. The British made their way to India via Azerbaijan, and Indian traders traded spices and cashmere fabrics in Baku and Shamakhi. Also, Baku previously served as a transit point for goods passing from China and India through the Black Sea to Constantinople.

Baku at the Crossroads of East and West

The Silk Road passes through many cities in the northwest direction. Baku, the capital of Azerbaijan, found at the crossroads of East and West, stayed the main administrative, political, cultural, ideological, handicraft and commercial center of the region. It is important that a Catalan map dated 1375 highlights the Caspian Sea as the "Baku Sea", as the city was also an important port. Many buildings from the days of the Great Silk Roads have been preserved in and around the capital, including the old town "Icherisheher", which includes the 15th century Shirvanshahs Palace, 5th-12th centuries. The Maiden's Tower, which is a unique monument of the 19th century, can be cited as examples of mosques, caravanserais, baths, tombs and madrasas as well as centuries. The 'Walled City of Baku', which includes the Shirvanshah's Palace and Maiden's Tower, is on the UNESCO World Heritage List.

The "Atashgah" temple, built by Indian Zoroastrian disciples known as Parsi, is another notable example of intercultural exchange in the city. According to Persian and Indian inscriptions, this temple was used as a Hindu, Sikh and Zoroastrian place of fire worship. Also included in the UNESCO World Heritage List, the Gobustan Rock Art Cultural Landscape is a rock art cultural reserve with an extraordinary collection of more than 6,000 rocks, encompassing the areas of a plateau of rocky rocks rising from the semi-desert of Central Azerbaijan.

An example of the fact that the country has passed through various stages of spiritual life throughout its long history is that it was initially ruled by beliefs and cults, and later by Zoroastrianism, which replaced Christianity in the 4th century. While most of the country's population has converted to Islam since the 7th century, it is the country's prerogative to enjoy a high level of religious tolerance. Today, as throughout history, there are synagogues, Christian churches and Zoroastrian temples as well as mosques. Tolerance is a feature reinforced for the Silk Roads period. At the junction of Europe and Asia, bordered by the Caspian Sea and the Caucasus Mountains, and having a prominent place on the Silk Road, the ancient network of trade routes connecting the East and the West, Azerbaijan, which has a key place on the Silk Road in the 19th century, is in Sheki on the northwest direction. As an international center for

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silk production, it was added to the UNESCO World Heritage list in July 2019, along with the Khan Palace.

Caravan Routes of the Silk Road

Since ancient times, the caravan routes of the Silk Road have always passed through Azerbaijan. Serving as the "gateway" between the mysterious faraway China and wealthy Europe, it has been called the busiest road through the Land of Lights in the 1st - 2nd centuries BC. The road, which started in Central Asia from China and India, passed through the territory of Azerbaijan by crossing the Uzbai river, which empties into the Caspian Sea. It would be correct to mention two routes here, the first of which leads upstream of the Kura River towards Colchis and Iberia, and the second that crosses the Derbent and Caucasian steppes along the western shore of a Caspian Sea.^[2] In addition to being one of the most important destinations of the Silk Road in ancient times, it is also important that it is durable, stable and dense. In the early Middle Ages, Azerbaijan continued to be an important center of the Silk Road. Barda, the capital of Azerbaijan in the 5th century, was considered the world's largest trading center on one of the branches of the Silk Road, and by the 10th century was one of the largest craft centers in the entire Middle East and Transcaucasia.

Iron Silk Road

A new railway crossing this important road is another prominent issue. Building the Baku-Tbilisi-Kars (BTK) railway, an "Iron Silk Road" connecting the oil-rich Caspian Sea region to Turkey, is an advance beyond Europe. Aside from thinking about the travels of ancient times, the fact that the 1200-kilometer-long piece of land known as the Caucasus between the Black Sea and the Caspian Sea takes its name from the mountain range where the excavated tunnels are found, increases its importance once again. The region served as a crossing point between Caucasus Europe and Asia before the Russian Empire; The fact that the old Silk Road passed through it has never made transportation between the West and the East so easy.

The Iron Silk Road is important for the newly independent republics of the South Caucasus – Georgia, Armenia and Azerbaijan – to regain strategic importance after the collapse of the Soviet Union in 1991, as it will open a new page in the history of the Caucasus. The realization of the enormous oil and gas reserves that lie below and along the Caspian Sea has also sparked a struggle to lay pipelines to the southern Caucasus to bring these resources to the European market. Today the pipelines are operational and BTK has been supported to support a trade boom by transporting European goods east and oil products west across the southern

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Caucasus. The railway starts in Baku, the capital of Azerbaijan, and continues through Tbilisi, Georgia, to Kars, a Turkish postal town at the southwest end of the Caucasus region.^[3]

Relations between Armenia and Turkey and the Silk Road

Looking directly to the east, Turkey has recently been trying to repair its relations with its neighbor Armenia. After helping Christian Armenia wage a bloody war on ethnic Armenians in the Azerbaijan enclave of Nagorno-Karabakh, in 1993, as a sign of loyalty to Azerbaijan, a close Turkish ally of the same Muslim religion, it closed the border and closed rail service with Armenia. The Armenians then demanded that Turkey admit that the massacres against its own people in 1915 constituted genocide, a situation Turkey denies.

Although there is a bridge between Turkey and Armenia, the Akhuryan River, which deeply cuts a valley that serves as a border between the two countries, is important for the Silk Road city of Ani.

Of course, seeing Kars, where the great wars between the Ottoman Turks and the Russians took place in the 19th century, could be changed by connecting the rich antipode in the Caspian to Baku and injecting new incomes into the local economy is of course another critical issue. It is difficult to explain how the railway made Kars "an important city in the eyes of the world". As Akhalkalaki is where the old railway from Georgia's capital Tbilisi ends, the 95-kilometer new track laying to Kars is a reminder that the factories in Ahalkalaki were disbanded after the Soviet collapse and their components sold under new capitalism. Ever since the farming collectives closed, the once fertile land has been overrun with weeds.^[4]

Georgia, Azerbaijan and Silk Road Projects

Now Georgia relies on the BTK railway to boost economic activity and help integrate this turbulent Armenian enclave with the rest of the country. There is still little hope in Ahalkalaki today that the new railway will alleviate this long post-communist resilience.

Baku no longer meets half of the world's oil needs, as it did at the beginning of the 20th century. In the years after former Turkish President Süleyman Demirel brought up the Iron Silk Road issue in a speech in Tbilisi in the late 1990s, interested parties have sought international funding for its construction. However, the Armenian diaspora blocked all funding efforts, convincingly arguing that, like the oil pipeline before it, routing the railway was a punitive gesture in connection with Nagorno-Karabakh.

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21st Century Technologies and Azerbaijan

Today, 21st Century technologies have changed the landscape of transportation, coordination and cargo transportation beyond recognition. However, Azerbaijan is once again at the forefront of transport infrastructure across the wider region, investing in major projects that will future-proof the country's export potential.

Since 2000, Baku, the capital of Azerbaijan, has been the Permanent Secretary of ICG TRACECA (Transport Corridor Europe-Caucasus-Asia), an international intergovernmental commission to strengthen economic relations, trade and transport links between the European Union and 12 member states, it is home to Europe, the Caucasus and the Central Asian region.

Initially funded by the European Commission, the project has been fully funded by member states since 2009. TRACECA has working groups covering maritime transport, aviation, road and rail, transport safety and transport infrastructure.

Modern Age and Azerbaijan

The EBRD is financing the renewal of the Silk Road in Azerbaijan. The new road will not only be safer, faster and less congested; It will also accelerate the international trade flow between Asia and Europe. Stretching from the capital Baku to the Georgian border, the 501-kilometer road is part of the wider link connecting Asia to Europe.^[5]

In our modern times, this path has become known as the “gut of Azerbaijan”. Not far outside Baku, the road faces West and winds through a desert for seemingly endless miles. This is reminiscent of Marco Polo's quote: "Whatever you do, never stray from the path."

Renewal of the Silk Road in Azerbaijan is one of the country's strategic projects. This route will allow the country to intensify its links with international trade flows between Asia and Europe. The new road will also make inland traffic easier and faster as car ownership and traffic levels increase rapidly.

Better conditions - and drastic measures on speed - will also make driving much safer and more comfortable.

The EBRD followed the project very closely from start to finish. The main reason for this is undoubtedly the massive travel improvements. The journey time from Baku to Kyurdamir has been reduced from two hours to less than one and a half hours. Kyurdamir is not known as the most attractive place in the country, but it is an important stopover between Azerbaijan, which borders the Caspian Sea, and Azerbaijan carved into the Caucasus mountains.

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Azerbaijan is found at the crossroads of major Eurasian land and air transport corridors. Since its independence, the Azerbaijani government has actively worked to make the country a bridge between Europe and Asia. Over the past decade, it has invested billions of dollars in commercial infrastructure and transportation projects. With the start of the construction of the Baku-Ahalkalaki-Kars railway, Baku airport is being transformed into a modern center.^[6]

The main idea of these projects is to position Azerbaijan as a lucrative link between Asia, Central Asia, South Caucasus and Europe. Baku understands the importance of implementing diversification strategies in anticipation of the depletion of the country's hydrocarbon reserves.

Part of the Silk Road still exists in the form of an asphalt highway connecting Pakistan and China's Xinjiang Uyghur Autonomous Region. The old road has been the driving force behind the United Nations' plan for a trans-Asian highway, and a rail equivalent of the road has been proposed by the UN Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific (UNESCAP). The road inspired Yo-Yo Ma in 1999 to set up the Silk Road Project, which explores cultural traditions along and beyond its route to unite world-class arts across cultures.

Silk Road and Turkey Connections

The Silk Road spanned the Asian continent and stood for a form of global economy when the known world was smaller but more difficult to traverse than it is today. A network of mostly land but also maritime trade routes, the Silk Road stretched from China in the east to Korea and Japan, connecting China via Central Asia to India in the south and Turkey and Italy in the west. The Silk Road system has been in existence for over 2000 years, with certain routes changing over time.

Since the concept of "Seidenstrassen" or "Silk Road" was first coined by the German geologist and explorer Baron Ferdinand von Richthofen in 1877, the "Silk Road" has been used as a metaphor for European and Asian cultural exchange. While largely commercial, the Silk Road provided a vehicle for all kinds of creative exchanges among an enormous variety of peoples and cultures.

Considering the symbolic meaning of sharing and exchange of the Silk Road, it is somewhat paradoxical that the desire to control the commodity of the same name, silk, is so strong. The ancient Chinese kept the secret of silk production for centuries. Ottoman Turks and Persians fought for it. The British and French competed to restrict their markets.^[7]

Terms Used for Silk

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The terms used for silk reveal its history and influences. Damascus silk, which refers to the Syrian style, is of Chinese origin. Silk chinoiserie is a European imitation of Chinese style, not Chinese. Martha Washington wore a Virginia silk dress to her husband's inauguration, and Native Americans learned to embroider silk to adorn traditional clothing. In the 19th century, Paterson, New Jersey, proclaimed itself the ubiquitous "Silk City."

Silk Road and Europe

The silk trade accelerated the commercial transformation of Western Europe. The practice of imitating Asian silk styles was institutionalized in Lyon, France, with the development of Chinese and Turkish motifs, chinoiserie and turqueserie, respectively. A steady stream of European travelers and adventurous traders transported luxury goods between Europe, the Middle East, Persia, India, and China. Jean-Baptiste Tavernier (1605-98), who crossed parts of the Silk Road on six journeys and witnessed the construction of Versailles, Isfahan, and the Taj Mahal, where diamonds and pearls were traded, was rewarded with an "Oriental" silk robe.^[8] The British developed their own silk industries and experimented with silk cultivation in Ireland and even in the New World.

In 1786, William Jones found connections between Sanskrit and Latin, contemplating the idea of an Indo-European language family. During the 19th century, European linguists studied the relations between European and Asian languages and considered such "families" to be the Uralic and Altaic languages. European scholars found common roots in religion and symbols that spanned Eurasia and linked Hinduism and Buddhism with ancient Greco-Roman mythology and Judaism, Islam, and Christianity. Archaeologists were beginning to find links between the widely scattered civilizations of Egypt, the Mediterranean, Mesopotamia, Persia, India, and Central Asia. Cultural diffusion, particularly strong in German and later British social science, became an explanatory model for the similarities found in vastly different societies and an alternative to cultural evolutionary theories. These connections between cultures, history and geography still interest us today.

Silk became both a part and a symbol of this cultural expansion. It was seen as a valuable index of civilization in terms of religious ritual, kingship, artistic production, and commercial activity. Silk represented higher things in life. It was a valuable, traded commodity and a historical medium of exchange. Silk played both an epitomized and a significant role in early development.

Central Asia and the Silk Road Today

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In formulating the idea of the Silk Road, Richthofen saw Central Asia not only as a land bridge between distant civilizations, but also as a source of cultural creativity. He also tried to portray it as a disputed territory, a region serving as a crossroads of political and military influence.^[9]

Although Central Asia was eclipsed by sea routes for several centuries in terms of trade, it has regained its historical importance recently and especially after 9/11. Its geopolitical importance increased as a result of the collapse of the Soviet Union, the need to achieve stable political states in the light of conflicting interests, and the need to find a suitable role for religion, especially Islam, in civilian life.^[10] Freedom in China and Kazakhstan marks a new evolution in contemporary jockeying for political influence and control.

Local Markets, Industries and Infrastructures

The nations of the region are trying to build their own post-Soviet and contemporary economies. They are taking part in an increasingly globalized world economy while struggling to develop local markets, industries and infrastructures. Some local entrepreneurs are trying to rebuild economies based on a traditional repertoire of deep-rooted Silk Road business skills. Emerging markets include recently discovered oil in Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan and western China.

Along the Silk Road, new social institutions such as universities, hospitals and financial systems are being built. Traditional knowledge embedded in Central Asian history promotes a contemporary renaissance of architecture and art. Historic sites are being restored.

Given the needs in the region, the work to build politically stable nations that are economically healthy, socially secure, and culturally self-confident is enormous and the forecast is far from definitive. However, it seems clear that people in the region have the best chance of improving their own and their children's lives by reclaiming their place in a transnational, intercultural flow of goods and ideas exemplified by the historic Silk Road. By protecting the Silk Road heritage, the region can once again play a significant role in the cultural and economic life of the global community.

Conclusion

In a three-level sense, today's Silk Road projects and studies bring historical echoes or traces. Three distinct types of infrastructure based on the movement of goods, services, people and ideas - the last one that sums up the openness and interconnectedness that shapes 'education' and informal learning in the broadest sense as words, speech, documents, exchange and abstract

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ideas that people learn from informal and formal contact. Being an element is at the core of the forward-looking 'education economy', which will also supply the infrastructure for a new digital Silk Road that will foster and encourage the lightning-fast exchange of ideas through innovative technologies. This is not an interconnection that is hard to imagine. On 22 June 2014, the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) named the Silk Road a World Heritage Site at the 2014 World Heritage Conference, with the United Nations World Tourism Organization's goal of promoting peace and understanding, The establishment of the National Silk Museum of China to commemorate the Silk Road becoming a UNESCO World Heritage Site since 1993, the declaration of "Silk Road Week" on June 19-25, 2020, in the literature on this subject. requires more studies and more research and scientific publications.

References

- "Belief Systems Along the Silk Road," Asia Society website, "Belief Systems Along the Silk Road". Archived from the original on 17 November 2016. Retrieved 17 November 2016. Retrieved 14 November 2016.
- "First 'Silk Road' train arrives in Tehran from China". Yahoo News. Archived from the original on 16 February 2016. Retrieved 16 February 2016.
- "Objectives". Archived from the original on 15 March 2013.
- "Seminar on Southwest Silk Road held in City". holiday. Archived from the original on 15 June 2013. Retrieved 17 April 2013.
- Anderson, James A. (2009). "China's Southwestern Silk Road in World History". *World History Connected*. 6 (1). Archived from the original on 9 February 2014. Retrieved 2 December 2013.
- Blue, G., & Brook, T. (Eds.). (1999). Introduction. In *China and historical capitalism: Genealogies of sinological knowledge* (pp. 1–9). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Bradsher, Keith (20 July 2013). "Hauling New Treasure Along the Silk Road". *The New York Times*. Archived from the original on 24 October 2014. Retrieved 22 July 2013.
- Chazizam, M. (2018). The Chinese Maritime Silk Road Initiative: The Role of the Mediterranean. *Mediterranean Quarterly*, 29(2), 54-69.
- Eliseeff (2009) [First published 1998]. "Approaches Old and New to the Silk Roads". *The Silk Roads: Highways of Culture and Commerce*. Berghahn Books. pp. 1–2. ISBN 978-92-3-103652-1, 1-57181-221-0, 1-57181-222-9
- Gan, Fuxi (2009). *Ancient Glass Research Along the Silk Road*. Shanghai Institute of Optics and Fine Mechanics, Chinese Academy of Sciences (Ancient Glass Research along the Silk Road, World Scientific ed.). p. 41. ISBN 978-981-283-356-3. Archived from the original on 27 February 2018.
- Gascoigne, Bamber; Gascoigne, Christina (2003), *The Dynasties of China: A History*, New York: Carroll and Graf Publishers, an imprint of Avalon Publishing Group, ISBN 978-0-7867-1219-9, p. 97.

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Global shipping and coordination chain reshaped as China's Belt and Road dreams take off" in Hellenic Shipping News, 4 December 2018.

Jerry Bentley, *Old World Encounters: Cross-Cultural Contacts and Exchanges in Pre-Modern Times* (New York: Oxford University Press, 1993), 33.

John Kelly (2005). *The Great Mortality: An Intimate History of the Black Death, the Most Devastating Plague of All Time* Harper. ISBN 978-0-06-000693-8

Kathy Ceceri, *The Silk Road : Explore the World's Most Famous Trade Route (White River Junction, VT: Nomad Press, 2011), 111.*

Kocka, J. (2016). *Capitalism: A brief history*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.

Neal, L. (Ed.). (2014). *The rise of capitalism, Vol 1, The Cambridge history of capitalism* (pp. 1–23). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Sophie Ibbotson and Max Lovell-Hoare (2016), *Uzbekistan, second edition, Bradt Travel Guides Ltd, pp. 12–13, ISBN 978-1-78477-017-4.*

Sun, Guangqi (1989), *History of Navigation in Ancient China*, Beijing: Ocean Press, ISBN 978-7-5027-0532-9

Vaissiere, EDL (2014). *Trans-Asian trade, or the silk road: Deconstructed (antiquity, Middle Ages)*. In L. Neal (Ed.), *The rise of capitalism, Vol 1, The Cambridge history of capitalism* (pp. one hundred–126). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Yang, J. (2015). *Transportation, boarding, lodging, and trade along the early silk road: A preliminary study of the Xuanquan manuscripts*. *Journal of the American Oriental Society*, 135(3), 421–432.

^[1] "Trade Requirements." UNESCO Knowledge Base, 2016.

^[2] Azerbaijan was the safest all the way. Georgia, Iberia, Colchis followed, politically stable states that could keep the route running and in turn attract traders. Another attraction was that most of the water transportation, which used to be the cheapest, involved transportation.

^[3] Turkey's accession marks a new alignment in a region often seen as Russia's backyard.

^[4] In Akhalkalaki and the surrounding Javakheti region, very few people speak Georgian and there is no one to teach it in schools. In the 1990s, the possibility arose that Javakheti could become Georgia's next separatist region, as did Abkhazia and South Ossetia in the north, which declared independence in the early 1990s but was largely unrecognized.

^[5] Explorers, traders, adventurers, and often armies traveled this route, which began in China in the 2nd century BC.

^[6] Billions have been invested in the road system, significantly reducing travel times between the Caspian Sea and the Azerbaijan-Georgia border, 550 kilometers west of Baku.

^[7] But despite such attempts, silk moved around the planet with remarkable ease and was a vehicle for cultural creativity wherever it went. The degree of borrowing and the choice of techniques and patterns, the invention and discovery of uses and styles are incredible. Every culture that touches silk has added humanity to its ornament.

^[8] Shah of Iran and XIV. A barony by Louis (for sale of what would later become the Diamond of Hope)

^[9] Indeed, control of the Silk Road, especially its Central Asian connection, was serious business for the 18th century colonial powers playing the "Great Game". Both the Russians and the British competed for control of Afghanistan on the verge of their territorial aspirations.

^[10] Recently, the US's entry into Central Asia, fighting the Taliban and al-Qaeda in Afghanistan, use of

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bases in Uzbekistan and Pakistan, and sovereignty in Kashmir, democracy in Iran, and the rights of ethnic

minorities in the west have become increasingly controversial. can be cited as examples.

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PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 **TELEFAX:** +49(177) 8684-353 **EMAIL :** ASI@EUROPE.DE